

BiMeGaFuel

Newsletter

 Ed. 3 – June 2026

**Bio Methanol Production via
Chemical Looping Gasification
Coupled with Membrane Reactors**

Project number: 101147737
Coordinator: Research Institute of Sweden
Project Coordinator: Amir Soleimani Salim
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www.biomegafuelproject.eu

WELCOME

- **Welcome to our third Newsletter!**

This edition features some of the latest news and interview with our partners. On our website www.biomegafuelproject.eu you will find public presentations, all the public deliverables of the project and many other interesting news. Please follow us!

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Meet the Team

Amir H. Soleimani Salim.
Researcher and project coordinator

I hold a Ph.D. in Chemical Engineering and a Diploma in Engineering Management and have conducted research across several leading universities and research institutes in Europe and North America in the field of bioenergy and industrial decarbonization, with a particular focus on BECCUS (Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Utilization/Storage) and broader carbon dioxide removal pathways. My work has centred on developing and assessing scalable solutions that combine biomass conversion, carbon management, and circular economy principles, with a strong emphasis on system integration and climate impact. In the Bio-MeGaFuel project, I will support the evaluation of scalability, sustainability, and negative emission potential, ensuring that the proposed solutions can effectively contribute to the decarbonisation of transport and chemical sectors.

Emil Hed
Research and Development Engineer

I am a chemical engineer and work with modelling and simulation of different chemical and physical processes and techno-economic analysis..

Sennai Asmelash Mesfun
Researcher

I am specialized in developing and assessing biorefinery processes. My work focuses on techno-economic evaluation, systems analysis, process integration, carbon efficiency, and GHG performance across integrated and stand-alone concepts.

Meet the Team

About RISE

Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE) is Swedish national research institute and innovation partner, and one of Europe's largest applied research organisations. As a state-owned and independent institute, RISE works across industry, academia and the public sector to accelerate innovation and support the development of technologies, products and services that contribute to a sustainable and competitive society. With more than 3,000 experts and over 130 testbeds and demonstration environments, RISE bridges the gap between research and real-world application in helping ideas move from early concept to scalable solutions. Its work spans areas such as life science, digital systems, materials, bioeconomy and built environment, always with a strong focus on sustainability, industrial renewal and societal impact.

In this project, RISE is the project coordinator and also the leader of WP4 - Process Evaluation and Sustainability Analysis

Project updates

The Bio-MeGaFuel project has successfully completed its first 18 months, making solid progress toward its overall objective of developing and demonstrating an integrated process for sustainable biomethanol production via chemical looping gasification (CLG) coupled with membrane reactor technology. Project implementation is broadly on track, with coordinated advances across management, experimental research, technology development, and exploitation activities.

Project management and coordination (WP1) are fully established and functioning effectively. Governance structures, communication channels, and reporting procedures are in place, supported by a Project Management Plan and a Data Management Plan aligned with FAIR principles. Key deliverables related to project coordination, administration, and data management have been completed, ensuring efficient execution and alignment with Grant Agreement requirements.

Significant technical progress has been achieved in chemical looping gasification (WP2). Representative biogenic feedstocks have been successfully selected and characterized (Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2), forming the basis for experimental campaigns. Small-scale CLG tests (1.5 kWth and 20 kWth) demonstrated high carbon conversion efficiencies (>90%) and provided critical insights into operating conditions, feeding behavior, and agglomeration risks. In parallel, a 500 kWth HTW[®] pilot campaign has been completed (>100 hours of operation), generating benchmark data. Preparations for 1 MWth CLG pilot-scale validation (milestone toward industrial relevance) are underway, while kinetic studies (D2.6) have started to support future modeling activities. Overall, WP2 has met key early milestones and reduced technical uncertainties related to fuel behavior, reactor operation, and scale-up.

Project updates

In membrane reactor development for biomethanol synthesis (WP3), good progress has been achieved. From month 1 to month 18, significant progress has been achieved in the fabrication and optimization of carbon membranes, including the investigation of key synthesis parameters and the scale-up of membrane length from lab-scale to pilot-relevant dimensions. In parallel, experimental activities for catalyst testing have been initiated, and the setup for lab-scale membrane reactor operation has been established. Substantial effort has also been devoted to the development and validation of advanced reactor models. These models have been used to support reactor design and optimization, demonstrating the potential advantages of membrane reactors over traditional configurations. Despite minor delays related to membrane fabrication issues, mitigation actions have been implemented and the overall progress of WP3 remains aligned with the project objectives, providing a solid basis for the upcoming scale-up and experimental validation activities.

WP4 (process evaluation, techno-economic and sustainability assessment) has not yet formally started (from M22), but preparatory alignment activities have been carried out. Initial discussions on process configurations, system boundaries, and modeling approaches have ensured readiness for upcoming work. This WP will play a central role in integrating technical results and assessing environmental, economic, and social performance, including life cycle assessment (LCA) and social LCA (s-LCA). The inclusion of these methodologies ensures the integration of social sciences and humanities (SSH), particularly through the evaluation of socio-economic impacts, value chains, and sustainability trade-offs, which are further supported by WP5 activities.

A graphic featuring a large green leaf on the left, a circular frame containing a green landscape with water, and the text 'Project updates' in bold black font. The background is a blurred image of green leaves.

Project updates

Exploitation, dissemination, and communication activities (WP5) have progressed well. A comprehensive market and production potential analysis for biomethanol (D5.1) has been completed, identifying shipping as the primary early market and the chemical sector as a key long-term market. Work on value chains and business models (D5.2) is advancing, highlighting critical bottlenecks such as feedstock logistics, and infrastructure needs. In parallel, dissemination and communication tools, including the project website, social media presence, workshops, and publications, are actively supporting stakeholder engagement, with key outputs such as dissemination strategies, communication materials, international workshops and webinars and active liaison with other EU partners.

Overall, the project has successfully delivered its planned early results, including multiple completed public deliverables (e.g., D1.3, D1.4, D2.1, D2.2, D5.1 and D5.5–5.10) and key milestones such as feedstock selection, pilot testing campaigns, and establishment of experimental and modeling frameworks. The project is progressing according to plan, with strong integration across work packages.

The next project period will focus on large-scale CLG demonstration (1 MWth), membrane reactor integration and validation, and the initiation of full process modeling and sustainability assessment, further advancing Bio-MeGaFuel toward its technological and commercial objectives.

Highlights & Updates

For more details on the events and highlights, please visit our project website

www.biomegafuelproject.eu

Jan 2026

26th Jan 2026, Bio-MeGaFuel and 2 EU projects, Bio-FlexCLC and COUPLED, co-hosted a webinar “Chemical Looping Processes”. At peak, there were 69 participants online.

Dr. Jochen Strohle from TUDA presented in the webinar “Chemical looping processes” with one general project presentation & one presentation on “Pilot testing of Chemical Looping Combustion for Biofuel Production”.

WEBINAR
Chemical Looping Processes

26 Jan 2026 10 AM 12 NN
Teams Link

Program

- 10:00 – 10:05 Intro – Prof. Fausto Gallucci
- 10:05 – 10:20 Projects Introduction
Prof. Vincenzo Spallina and Dr. Amir Soleimani Salim
- 10:20 – 10:45 Flexible Chemical Looping Combustion Pathways for Sustainable Bioenergy Conversion
Prof. Tobias Mattisson (Bio-FlexCLC)
- 10:45 – 11:10 Enabling low carbon chemical production via chemical looping: technology scale up and process feasibility
Prof. Vincenzo Spallina (COUPLED)
- 11:10 – 11:35 Pilot Testing of Chemical-Looping Gasification for Biofuel Production
Dr. Jochen Ströhle (Bio-MeGaFuel)
- 11:35 – 11:50 Closure and roundtable

Join us at

CUBE

WEBINAR on Chemical Looping processes

21:31

FG RM S AD BB AC

Aim

Develop a novel, efficient, and scalable process to convert low-value biogenic residues and organic waste to biomethanol through chemical looping gasification coupled with membrane reactors

Chemical Looping Webinar, 2026

Funded by the European Union

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Highlights & Updates

Feb 2026

25th – 26th Feb 2026, Bio-MeGaFuel and 2 EU projects, MemCat and HERMES, co-organized the 3rd Winter School on “Gasification and Membrane Reactor” in Microlab, Eindhoven. This winter school is a joint communication activity among EU projects early researchers and students in this field. For this event, 33 researchers from all over Europe presented. CSIC and ICUBE did oral presentations for WP2 & WP3, while Perpetual Next and GIDARA Energy B.V. presented from industrial perspectives.

PROGRAM	
1st Day: 25th February 2026	
8:30 - 9:00	Registration, Coffee and Introduction
9:00 - 10:00	Dr. Shafiqi Graham (Perpetual Next N.V.) Transformation as a enabler for the production of biomethanol from organic residues via anaerobic bio-pretreatment
10:00 - 11:00	Dr. Francisco Garcia Labajos (The Spanish National Research Council) CSIC Chemical Leaching Gasification process at Bio-MegaFuel
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break & posters
11:30 - 12:30	Dr. Anilbek Gost (GIDARA Energy b.v.) Fluidized Bed Gasification for Producing Sustainable Fuels and Chemicals from Biomass and Waste
12:45 - 14:00	Lunch
14:00 - 15:00	Dr. Verena Müllersiep (Flemish Institute for Technological Research VITO) Multi-Scale Studies of Membrane reactor and 3D printed reactors
15:00 - 16:00	Dr. Mert Karadas (Turkish Petroleum Refineries Corporation TİPRAŞ) HERMES for Coax Refining: Innovative Refinery Applications
16:00 - 16:30	Coffee break & posters
16:30 - 17:30	Dr. Zeynep Sahin (Muhleita b.v.) A Cloud Asses Infrastructure for commercial membrane reactor models
19:00	Social Dinner
2nd Day: 26th February 2026	
8:30 - 9:00	Welcome and Coffee
9:00 - 10:00	Prof. Domenico Borrelli (Sapienza University of Rome) Fluidized Bed Gasification of Waste: Emerging Trends and Innovation Potential
10:00 - 11:00	Prof. Sergio Sartorio (University of Calabria) Advanced Membranes and Processes for Water Vapor Separation and Recovery
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee break & posters
11:30 - 12:30	Prof. Vincenzina Spallone (Manchester University) Liquid waste recovery for the production of SAF: lessons learnt from H2O2 GLIMPUR
12:45 - 14:00	Lunch
14:00 - 15:00	Dr. Omer David (Technalia Research & Innovation) Hollow fiber membranes for gas separation: from polymer design to membrane processing
15:00 - 16:00	Prof. Ferrate Cellucci (Eindhoven University of Technology) Membrane and membrane reactor for CO ₂ hydrogenation
16:00 - 16:30	Poster Awards & closure

Highlights & Updates

Feb 2026

19th Feb 2026, CSIC joined the webinar with European Gas Research Group (GERG). Francisco García Labiano (CSIC) was invited to give a talk of 20 min about "Advances, Applications and Opportunities of Chemical Looping Technologies for Carbon Capture", followed by Q&A of 15 minutes. The peak of participants was 18. This meeting was not opened to public audience it was only for the GERG members.

Mar 2026

6th March 2026, our partners participated in a webinar with other 3 EU projects entitled "Electrolysis and Gasification". Project coordinator gave a general introduction of the project & Fausto Gallucci gave a presentation "Membrane reactions for Methanol and for DME production". At peak, there were 98 participants online.

GeniusFuels Thematic webinar
 Friday 6th March 2026
 15:00 (CET)

"Electrolysis and Gasification: possible synergies in energy and fuel production"

Agenda:
 15:00 Welcome and introduction
 15:15 GeniusFuels: "Electrolysis and Gasification a win-win relation in energy and fuel production"
 15:35 Bio-MeGaFuel: "Bio-Methanol Production via Chemical Looping Gasification Coupled with Membrane Reactors" and "Membrane reactors for Methanol and for DME production"
 15:55 BeBOP: "Biomass to bio/E-methanol by Breakthrough SOEC-based Process: the BeBOP innovation"
 16:15 OUTFOX: "Optimised Up-Scaled Technology for Next-Generation Solid Oxide Electrolysis"
 16:30 Discussion
 16:55 Concluding remarks

REGISTER NOW:

Organizers:
 andrea.koolen2@unibo.it
 nikolaos.dimitrakou@unibo.it
 giulia.balera2@unibo.it

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Highlights & Updates

May 2026

4th May 2026, Bio-MeGaFuel kick-off the project cluster “CL&G” with 5 projects – Bio-FlexCLC, BioNETzero, COUPLED, HYIELD and PYRAH2. The cluster will create a shared platform for workshops, events, and joint outreach to increase the visibility of results and encourage uptake by policymakers, industry, and research communities.

Bio-MeGaFuel

Press Release

New EU research cluster targets green hydrogen and renewable fuels from biomass and waste

13 April 2026

Six EU-funded projects are combining expertise in chemical looping and gasification to accelerate the production of green hydrogen and renewable fuels from biomass and waste. The technology they are developing will also enable efficient CO₂ capture.

The projects are forming a collaborative cluster, set to launch formally in May 2026, to connect their complementary approaches and strengthen cooperation. Other EU-funded projects and initiatives working in related fields are welcome to join. Those interested are encouraged to contact the organising team.

While each project addresses a specific technological pathway, they share a common focus: converting biomass and waste-derived feedstocks into valuable products such as hydrogen, syngas, and renewable fuels. The cluster will create a shared platform for workshops, events, and joint outreach to increase the visibility of results and encourage uptake by policymakers, industry, and research communities.

Further details on the cluster's activities will be announced following its official launch.

Participating projects:
[Bio-FlexCLC](#) - [Bio-MeGaFuel](#) - [BioNETzero](#) - [COUPLED](#) - [HYIELD](#) - [PYRAH2](#)

Acknowledgements

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Upcoming events

www.biomegafuelproject.eu

31st Aug – 4th Sep

International Conference on Chemical Looping
ICCL 2026, Manchester, United Kingdom

10th Sep

M24 GA meeting
Blue World Technologies, Denmark

Coming soon

Joint workshop and webinar

www.biomegafuelproject.eu

BiMeGaFuel

Bio Methanol Production via Chemical Looping Gasification Coupled with Membrane Reactors

Contact

- @ Project Coordinator:
amir.soleimani.salim@ri.se
- @ Dissemination Manager:
s.scoppa@1cube.eu

Follow us

Website

LinkedIN

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 TOPIC: HORIZON-CL5-2023-D3-02-07
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 Coordinator: RISE Research Institute of Sweden

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